

up to 68 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) (A) plants at flowering (see figure).

A lines of experimental hybrids are planted five times at an 8-10 d interval. This staggered planting ensures a continuous supply of flowering A plants to synchronize with the flowering of R lines in different seed production plots. A lines are planted upwind from R lines and near the seed production plots to facilitate the transport of plants.

When primary tillers of A and R lines are at booting, their flag leaves are clipped. The two outermost border rows in the R plots are not clipped to demarcate the plots and to act as a barrier to pollen from adjoining plots. Three to five d after clipping, A plants are uprooted and relocated to the vacant spaces. Uprooting is done between 0630 h and 0800 h to reduce shock. A line plants are not used if more than 20% of their spikelets have already bloomed.

Pollen dispersal is increased at peak anthesis (1030 h to 1100 h) by shaking R line panicles with a bamboo stick. Pollen

Layout for isolation-free system for producing experimental rice hybrid seed.

movement to the adjoining plots is minimized by disturbing only R plants immediately surrounding the A plants. Supplementary pollination is done for 5-7 d or until pollen of a R line is exhausted. R line plants from seed production plots are harvested first, followed by A plants bearing the (A × R) F₁ seeds.

Two CMS lines yielded 4-5 g hybrid seed/plant during wet season and 7-10 g seed/plant during dry season using this system. Five to ten plants of a CMS line can produce 40 g of experimental hybrid seed for evaluation in an observation yield trial for two seasons. Twenty to 40 plants can produce 150 g experimental hybrid seed for evaluation in a replicated preliminary yield trial for two seasons.

We have been using the isolation-free seed production system at IRRRI for the past three seasons. During 1992, we produced seeds of 103 experimental hybrids for evaluation in preliminary yield trials. Seed contamination was 0-8%, with a mean of 1.7%.

We strongly recommend that hybrid rice breeders in national programs use this system for producing experimental hybrid rice seed for evaluation in preliminary yield trials. ■

Identifying maintainer and restorer lines for hybrid rice in Himachal Pradesh (HP), India

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Identifying maintainer and restorer lines in traditional varieties (TVs) and modern varieties (MVs) adapted to the agroclimatic conditions of HP is a prerequisite to initiating a hybrid rice program in the state. Cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line V20 A, which possesses wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm, seems ideally suited for this purpose.

Identified maintainer and restorer lines^a of V20 A at HPKV, Palampur, HP, India, 1991 wet season.

Cultivar	Based on	
	Pollen fertility	Spikelet fertility
Himadhan	M	M
R575	M	M
Kaladhan	M	M
CH1039	M	M
IR18482-Plp3-2-5-2	M	M
HPU2202	M	M
Debal	M	M
HPU5101	M	M
CH988	M	M
K39	PR	PR
Himalaya 741	-	PR
HPU799	-	PR
HPU2216	-	PR
IR9129-263-3-3-2-3-2	-	PR
HPU5039-Plp13-4-4-6-3B	PR	PR

^aM = effective maintainer (0% fertility), PR = partial restorer (10-69% pollen fertility and 10-79% spikelet fertility).

A set of 16 locally used TVs and MVs were crossed with V20 A, which was used as the female parent. Five spikelets were selected from each plant before anthesis and fixed in 70% alcohol. Two or three anthers from each spikelet were placed together on a glass slide and squashed in 1% iodine solution. Slides were screened for sterile/fertile pollen. Estimates were based on five panicles from bagged hybrid plants.

Maintainers and restorers for V20 A were identified based on pollen and spikelet fertility (see table). Maintainers

were more frequent than restorers. Himdhan, R575, Kaladhan, CH1039, IR18482-Plp3-2-5-2, HPU2202, Debal, HPU5101, and CH988 had 100% pollen sterility and were identified as effective maintainers for V20 A.

Pollen fertility did not show any correlation ($r = 0.24$) with spikelet fertility. Therefore, spikelet fertility was used to identify restorers. Effective restorers have spikelet fertility of 80% and above.

K39, Himalaya 741, HPU799, HPU2216, IR9129-263-3-3-2-3-2, and

HPU5039-Plp13-4-4-6-3B were classified as partial restorers, which means spikelet fertility is less than 80% but 10% or more.

These findings indicate that effective maintainers are common among rice cultivars adapted to HP's conditions. New CMS lines possessing WA cytoplasm and from different genetic backgrounds can be developed by recurrent backcrossing procedure. Effective restorers for WA cytoplasm still need to be identified among locally adapted rice cultivars to develop heterotic rice hybrids. ■

Maintainers and restorers for four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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Screening elite breeding lines for effective and genetically diverse maintainers and restorers for different CMS lines is important in developing new CMS lines and productive hybrids.

Short-, medium-, and long-duration rice cultivars were used as pollen parents for crossing with WA-type CMS lines PMS-3 A, PMS-10 A, IR62829 A, and V20 A. The F_1 hybrids were evaluated for spikelet fertility during the 1992 wet season (WS).

Rice cultivars with 80% or more spikelet fertility were classified as effective restorers, those with 1-79% as partial restorers, and those with less than 1% as effective maintainers.

All the test cultivars except IET10485, IET11831, IET12395, and RR8585 were identified as effective maintainers (see table). IET11831 proved to be an effective restorer for PMS-3 A and PMS-10 A, and a partial restorer for IR62829 A. IET10749 restored the fertility of PMS-10 A but maintained the sterility of PMS-3 A and IR62829 A. IET10485 and IET12395, however, partially restored the fertility of IR62829 A and PMS-3 A, respectively. Only RR8585 restored the fertility of all four CMS lines. ■

Maintainers and restorers for PMS-3 A, PMS-10 A, IR62829 A, and V20 A.^a RARS, R. S. Pura, India, 1992 WS.

Variety	CMS lines			
	PMS-3 A	PMS-10 A	IR62829 A	V20 A
RR8585	R	R	R	R
IET10485	M	-	PR	-
IET10749	M	R	M	-
IET11074	M	M	M	-
IET11831	R	R	PR	-
IET12395	PR	-	M	-
IET12403	-	M	-	R
IET13152	-	M	-	M
Kasturi	M	M	-	M
R. Basmati	M	M	M	M
Giza 14 (japonica)	M	M	M	-

^aR = restorer, PR = partial restorer, M = maintainer.

Identifying maintainers and restorers of cytoplasmic genetic male sterile (CMS) lines for hybrid rice breeding

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We used 25 varieties as male parents to make 132 crosses with CMS lines V20 A, IR46830 A, IR54752 A, ES18 A, Madhu A, Pragathi A, Pushpa A, and Mangla A (Table 1) to identify maintainers and restorers with varying tolerance for agroclimatic stress and resistance to biotic stress.

Pollen from each CMS line was tested with 1% iodine solution before crossing and found to have a high degree of

sterility. The pollen parents and F_1 s were transplanted together to determine maintainers and restorers. Panicles were bagged before emergence to avoid outcrossing.

Spikelet fertility of F_1 s and parents (10 plants each) was recorded at the Crop Research Station (CRS), Masodha, Faizabad, during 1987-90 wet seasons

Table 1. CMS lines used in the study.

CMS line	Origin	Source of cytoplasm
V20 A	China	Wild abortive
IR46830 A	IRRI	Wild abortive
IR54752 A	IRRI	Wild abortive
ES18 A	India	MS 577
Madhu A	India	MS 577
Pragathi A	India	MS 577
Pushpa A	India	MS 577
Mangla A	India	MS 577